

Assessment of the ionospheric scintillation over Portugal – ALERT Activity report

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1. Abstract

Until recently, it was widely accepted that scintillation events do not pose any significant danger to GNSS-based technologies at middle latitudes. However, the sensitivity of GNSS instruments and their abundance constantly grow resulting in a concern of GNSS-users about impacts of ionospheric scintillations on the quality of the GNSS signal in the middle latitudes. Some studies were performed to assess the recurrence and the amplitude of ionospheric irregularities at middle latitudes (Mrak et al., 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020RS007131>), still, no such studies were ever performed for Portugal. The occurrence of potential ionospheric scintillation affecting low elevation southward GNSS measurements from receivers in Southern Europe can be studied using the S4 and ROTI scintillation indices computed from permanent GNSS receivers located in Southern Europe, during geomagnetically quiet and active periods.

Unfortunately, there are not many data sets of scintillation indices (SI), such as S4 and ROTI, that cover the SW part of the Europe (Iberian Peninsula). The IA-UC team already has access to a significant amount of GNSS SI observations made between November 2014 and February 2019 at Lisbon airport in the frame of one of our previous projects SWAIR (ESA Small Artes, 2014-2022, see Barlyaeva et al., 2020). This data set generated by a GNSS receiver with the SCINDA software consists of the total electron content (TEC) and SI data, available both in the SCINDA and ASCII format (Morozova et al., 2022b). The TEC data were already analysed, verified, and used for several studies (Morozova et al., 2020, 2022a), but the SI data still need to be verified.

Preliminary tests of the SCINDA SI (S4 and ROTI) series (Oliveira and Morozova, 2022) suggest that there are no significant flaws in the observational series, however the full data set still needs a detailed verification.

We contacted the INGV scintillation group that runs the eSWua database which includes scintillation data as well. We would like to validate our scintillation data and put them in the context of supporting the European capabilities of scintillation monitoring by providing access to this data set through eSWua. An open access to this data will be beneficial for the ionospheric community: the ionospheric scintillations in the SW part of the Europe are poorly studied because of the limited amount of the observational data.

We expect that work done during both the PITHIA-TNA project we propose and further collaboration projects with the INGV group will help to fill this knowledge gap and will be beneficial both for the Portuguese and Italian ionosphere communities and would increase the monitoring capabilities in the Mediterranean area.

2. Scientific objectives

The IA-UC team has access to about of 4 years (November 2014 – February 2019) of more or less continuous measurements of ionospheric conditions for a SW European location (Lisbon). These measurements were made by a GNSS receiver with the SCINDA software that produced

1 min data (the total electron content (TEC), the scintillation indices (SI) S4 and ROTI as well as elevation and azimuth for each of the observed GPS satellites). The receiver was not calibrated during the installation, therefore, its measurements need to be verified using, for example, data from close receivers.

A short study was performed to analyse the behaviour of the SCINDA SI data during several month of 2015 (March, June, September, October, December, months with most significant geomagnetic storms of this year) – see Oliveira and Morozova (2022). We obtained promising results: SI seems to behave during the quiet and disturbed days in a way that is expected for the studied region of the European middle latitudes. However, before this data set is used for further scientific analysis the whole data set must be verified. Such verification is the 1st part of the proposed ALERT project.

After the verification of the SCINDA SI data they may be included by the INGV team into the eSWua scintillation database.

The verified SCINDA SI data set in combination with the INGV eSWua scintillation data will be used further to study ionospheric scintillations at the Mediterranean region: the scintillation events observed at Lisbon (most western part of the Mediterranean region) will be compared with scintillations observed by Italian instruments.

3. Work plan

1. Validate the SCINDA SI data set;
2. Check possibilities to incorporate it into the INGV database;
3. Study scintillation events at middle latitudes seen at the Portuguese and Italian regions during geomagnetic storms.

4. Visit report and Project main results

On February 6-10, 2023, A. Morozova visited INGV group and discussed with L. Spogli, C. Cesaroni and their colleagues to discuss the verification process, possibility to incorporate IA-UC data to eSWua and to select scintillation events for the further analysis.

As a result,

1. A site characterisation and the data validation procedures were agreed to be applied to the IA-UC data after the visit;
2. Unfortunately, the IA-UC data found to be produced by an instrument (a geodetic GNSS receiver with SCINDA software and 1 min cadence) of different design and data quality acquisition comparing to instruments used to build eSWua data base. Different instruments available in eSWua repository. These are professional Ionospheric Scintillation Monitor Receivers (Bougard et al, 2011) able to sample GNSS signals at a 50 Hz frequency and calculate the amplitude and phase scintillation indices on a 1 minute basis.

3. A scintillation event on June 22-23, 2015, was selected for a case study; it was decided to update the list of the studied scintillation events after the data set validation is finished.

The results of the data set validation are presented below (Section 5) with preliminary results for the June 2015 event. A detailed analysis of the scintillation events is in progress, some results will be presented at ESWW 2023 meeting in Toulouse in November 2023 (poster SWR03-592).

5. Scientific report

5.1. Data

To analyse scintillation occurrence a historical data on the amplitude scintillation index S4 obtained from a geodetic Septentrio GNSS receiver with SCINDA software installed in Lisbon airport (38.8° N, 9.1° W) between December 2014 and February 2019 in the frame of the SWAIR project (Barlyaeva et al., 2020; Morozova et al., 2023; data: Barlyaeva et al., 2020; Morozova et al., 2022). The S4 values were calculated by SCINDA software (as well as, for example, the ROTI index and the total electron content, TEC). The dataset has 1 min time resolution and allows to identify S4 values for each of the available at a moment GPS satellite. Only satellites with elevation above 9.8° are used (hardware induced cut-off).

A preliminary analysis of this S4 dataset (hereafter, Lisbon S4 dataset) was performed in (Oliveira and Morozova, 2022), This analysis showed certain reasonable pattern in the S4 variations and can be considered as a preliminary validation test.

5.2. Site characterisation

5.2.1. Comparison to other S4 data

As first step to validate the Lisbon S4 dataset we compared S4 data from this dataset with S4 observations for Lampedusa site (eSWua data base, <http://www.eswua.ingv.it/>). A direct comparison between the data series is not possible because of different types of the receivers: a geodetic receiver with SCINDA software in Lisbon and a scintillation receiver in Lampedusa.

Due to the cut-off on the satellites' elevation of 9.8° used by the SCINDA receiver, only data from satellites with elevation $\geq 9.8^\circ$ were used for the analysis of the Lampedusa series. On the other hand, both receivers use only GPS satellites, thus no correction of the used satellites is needed.

To compare the SCINDA and eSWua S4 series we averaged S4 values for different time intervals (1 min, 15 min, 1 h and 1 day). Corresponding plots are shown in [Fig. 1](#) for June 2015. As one can see, while there are differences between the series, the general trends, that seem to be clearer with larger averaging time window, are similar. The daily patterns seem very similar as well, and an increase of S4 on June 22, the day of an intense geomagnetic storms associated with known scintillation event, is also clearly visible in both series. The higher amplitude of

this increase in the SCINDA data is, most probably, related to a westward position of the Lisbon receiver. Due to a westward position the Lisbon receiver seems to record more scintillation events than the Lampedusa receiver because of the shape of the geomagnetic equator in the European-African sector.

Figure 1. Comparison of S4 series obtained for Lisbon and Lampedusa in June 2015: (a) 1 min, (b) 15 min, (c) 1 hour and (d) 1 day averages.

Correlation coefficients r between the Lisbon and Lampedusa series calculated for different time interval and for series with different time averaging are shown in [Tab. 1](#). As one can see, while the absolute values of r are small, they still hint on similarity between the series, especially during the storm day. Thus, the Lisbon S4 series can pass to the second evaluation stage.

Table 1. Correlation coefficients r between the Lisbon and Lampedusa S4 series for June 2015.

Averaging	Time interval					
	1-28 June	1-20 June	1-10 June	10-20 June	20-28 June	22 June
15 min	0.22	0.18	0.23	0.15	0.26	0.41
1 hour	0.33	0.28	0.33	0.24	0.40	0.61
1 day	0.52			-		

5.2.2. Multipath signal

The initial test showed that the Lisbon S4 dataset contain relevant S4 data. Now these data must be studied to see if they are contaminated by multipath signals. This contamination must be identified and removed or marked up, i.e. a site characterization must be performed before any further analysis of scintillation patterns.

To perform the site characterization the latitudes and longitudes of the ionospheric pierce points (IPP) were calculated for each of the S4 observations using the data on satellites azimuth and elevation. [Fig. 2\(a-f\)](#) shows plots of S4 (colour) as a function of the IPP local time: DOY (day-of-year) and hour. As one can see, the Lisbon S4 dataset contains a significant amount of multipath signal (diagonal lines corresponding to individual satellites), however, in most cases the multipath-related S4 values do not exceed 0.4-0.5. Thus, by setting a threshold to $S4 = 0.5$ or even $S4 = 0.6$ we can eliminate most of the multipath-related contamination.

Another feature that is prominent on these plots are “scintillation events” – several-hours long periods with high S4 values seen as coloured vertical stripes.

5.3. S4 data quality

The quality of the S4 data is not constant between December 2014 and February 2019. Starting from 2017 the number of observations with $S4 \geq 1$ increases drastically. [Figure 3\(a-f\)](#) show S4 values as a function of the IPP local time but only for low elevation ($< 20^\circ$) satellites. As one can see comparing corresponding plots of [Figs. 2](#) and [3](#), most of the multipath signals are related to the low elevation satellites. Also, before 2017 most of high values of S4 were also obtained for low elevation satellites. However, starting from 2017, but most prominently in 2018-2019, high S4 values were very often obtained for high elevation satellites. This is clearly seen in [Figs. 4-5\(a-f\)](#) that show S4 values as function of IPP latitude and longitude for all ([Fig. 4](#)) and low elevation ([Fig. 5](#)) satellites. This sudden change of S4 distribution (drastic increase of high S4 values, especially for high elevation satellites) has no known natural source and, to our mind, is artificial.

Figure 2. S4 variations (colour scheme) as function of IPP local time: day (X axis) and hour (Y axis) for 2014 (a, December only), 2015 (b), 2016 (c), 2017 (d), 2018 (e) and 2019 (f, January-February only). Blue lines show sunrise and sunset time at the receiver latitude (solid line) and at the equator (dashed line) on the ionosphere altitude (300 km).

Figure 3. Same as Figure 2, but for low elevation satellites.

The data series from the SCINDA receiver installed in the Lisbon airport in the frame of the SWAIR project have many gaps caused by malfunctioning of the receiver and its re-initialization. Most probably, some of the re-starts of the receiver's software or re-installation of its antenna that happens between 2017 and 2018 were not performed correctly, resulting in drastic decrease of S4 data quality. That the quality of the TEC series from the same dataset also decreases at about the same time.

Same conclusions can be made by analysing time variations of S4 during a day for individual years ([Figs. 6, 7 and 8](#), for all, high and low elevation satellites, respectively). As one can see, a certain pattern in daily S4 variability (most of the high S4 values are obtained for the night-to-morning hours)

- Is clearly seen for 2014-2016,
- is slightly disturbed in 2017 (events in March and June 2017),
- fully disappear in 2018-2019 due to high variability of S4 data.

This daily pattern and its distortions are seen both in the high and low elevation data ([Figs. 7-8](#)). Also, as is clearly seen from comparison of [Figs 7 and 8](#), in 2018-2019 the high S4 values are obtained mostly for the high elevation satellites, not for low elevation satellites as in 2014-2017 (with exception of March, June and, possibly, August 2017).

Azimuthal distributions of S4 for individual years is shown in [Figs. 9, 10 and 11](#) for all, high and low elevation satellites, respectively, and the elevation distributions of S4 for individual years is shown in [Fig. 12](#). An analysis of these figures confirms significant changes in the S4 data quality in 2018-2019 and in March, June and, possibly, in August 2017.

Figure 4. S4 variations (colour scheme) as function of IPP coordinates: longitude (X axis) and latitudes (Y axis) for 2014 (a, December only), 2015 (b), 2016 (c), 2017 (d), 2018 (e) and 2019 (f, January-February only). Cross mark the receiver position.

Figure 5. Same as Figure 4 but for low elevation satellites.

Figure 6. S4 variations as function of an hour for 2014 (a, December only), 2015 (b), 2016 (c), 2017 (d), 2018 (e) and 2019 (f, January-February only).

Figure 7. Same as Figure 6 but for high elevation satellites.

Figure 8. Same as Figure 6 but for low elevation satellites.

Figure 9. S4 variations as function of an azimuth for 2014 (a, December only), 2015 (b), 2016 (c), 2017 (d), 2018 (e) and 2019 (f, January-February only).

Figure 10. Same as Figure 9 but for high elevation satellites.

Figure 11. Same as Figure 9 but for low elevation satellites.

Figure 12. S4 variations as function of a satellites' elevation for 2014 (a, December only), 2015 (b), 2016 (c), 2017 (d), 2018 (e) and 2019 (f, January-February only).

5.4. Preliminary conclusions

The SCINDA S4 series can be used for scintillation events analysis for the December 2014 – December 2016 time interval, and with care for the year 2017, taking into account abnormal scintillation events in March, June and August 2017. The data for 2018-2019 are contaminated by artificial scintillation events.

To eliminate the multipath signal a simple filtering $S4 > 0.5$ or $S4 > 0.6$ can be used as a first step with individual analysis of specific cases if necessary.

5.5. Comments on the 2017 data

To clean the S4 data for 2017, days with anomalous (very high) S4 values appearing after a break in the data records were identified (days 18 and 19 in March, days 7, 13, 16 to 19 in June and days 12 and 13 in August) and the corresponding S4 values were deleted from the records. Fig. 13 show S4 corrected series for 2017 as functions of IPP DOY and hour (a), IPP latitude and longitude (b), hour (c), satellites azimuth (d) and elevation (e); these figures correspond to [Figs. 2d](#), [4d](#), [6d](#), [9d](#), and [12d](#), respectively. The corrected S4 series for 2017 seems to have distributions closer to ones for 2014-2016, however, this data set still must be analysed with care.

Figure 13. Corrected S4 variations for 2017 as function of IPP DOY and hour (a), IPP latitude and longitude (b), hour (c), satellites azimuth (d) and elevation (e), See [Figs. 2d](#), [4d](#), [6d](#), [9d](#), and [12d](#), respectively, for comparison

6. Analysis of the Lisbon S4 data for 2014-2016

To take advantage of the good quality Lisbon S4 data between December 2014 and December 2016, the analysis of scintillation events started from this data set.

6.1. General scintillation patterns

The analysis of the S4 variations during a day (see, e.g., [Figs. 6a-c](#) and [13c](#) for individual years, [Fig 14](#) for all observations from 2014 to 2017 and Supplementary Figures [S1-S3](#) for individual months) shows that:

1. In most cases, scintillation events (observation of the several in a row S4 values above a threshold of 0.6, hereafter **SE**) are observed in the local post-sunset hours (from 18-19 h) and the post-midnight (until 5 h) hours. In some cases, SEs were observed during the day hours (see an analysis of individual SEs below).

2. There is no dependence on the geomagnetic activity level and appearance of SEs: as one can see from Figures [S1-S3](#), there are both geomagnetic disturbances accompanied and not accompanied by SEs, as well as SEs during geomagnetically quiet times.
3. The visual analysis shows no prominent seasonal dependence in the SEs appearance, however when the individual SEs were identified, it was found that out of 39 SEs that took place between December 2014 and December 2016,
 - 26 SEs happened in February-to-April;
 - 10 SEs happened from September to December.
4. The length of the studied time interval (25 months with reliable data) does not allow to detect a clear dependence of SEs appearance on the solar cycle, however we can report 35 SEs in 2015 and only 2 in 2016.

Figure 14. S4 variations for 2017 as function of hour from December 2014 to December 2016.

6.2. Scintillation events observed from December 2014 to December 2016

As was mentioned before, 39 SEs were identified between December 2014 and December 2016. They are listed in [Tab. 2](#).

As one can see, most of the scintillation events took place during geomagnetically quiet conditions and only six of SEs took place during geomagnetic storms (considering the threshold of $Dst \leq -50$ nT as geomagnetic disturbance indicator, there were at least 16 geomagnetic disturbances, 10 of them were geomagnetic storms with $Dst \leq -95$ nT).

Considering the length of SE, 24 events were a brief event when high S4 values were observed during less than 1 hour, while the remaining 15 SEs lasted up to 4-5 hours (marked as “Long” in [Tab. 2](#)) and consisted of several briefer sub-events.

Most of SEs were post-sunset events (PS), seven or eight of them were extended over the local midnight (PS+PM events), however there were five SEs that were solely post-midnight events (PM).

In most cases, SEs were single night events, however in April 2015 (SE #23-24 and 25-26) and in October 2015 (SE # 32-33) there were three events when scintillation were observed during two nights in a row.

Concerning the azimuthal and elevation position of satellites experiencing SEs, in all cases high S4 values were observed for satellites located southward from the receiver (azimuthal range 120-240°). Also, in all cases except SE # 29 (June 22-23, 2015), the scintillations were observed for low elevation satellites only. The IPP associated with high S4 values are concentrated in an area between 25° N and 35° N in latitude and between 12° W and 5° W in longitude (the N-W part of the Africa and Canary Islands).

Among the found SEs most interest present 15 so-called long events, and the event #29 that took place during the night June 22-23, 2015, is of the highest interest, were selected for the further analysis to be performed outside the frame of the PITHIA-TNA project ALERT. for the further analysis. Some preliminary results for the June 22-23, 2015, event are presented below (see also Morozova and Spogli, 2023).

Table 2. Scintillation events (SEs) between December 2014 and December 2016: date and hours (UTC) when a SE is observed, azimuthal, elevation (L – low elevation satellites only, A – all satellites), IPP latitudinal and longitudinal ranges, geomagnetic conditions (during a geomagnetic storm? Y/N) and classification (PS – post-sunset, PM – post-midnight).

N	Date	Time interval	Classification	Azimuth range	Elevation range	IPP		GM storm (Y/N)	Comments
						Latitudinal range, N	Longitudinal range, W		
1	21.12.2014	~20 h; 22-24 h	PS	~160-190°	L	25-35°	10-5°	N	
2	24.12.2014	~1 h	PM	~170°	L	27°	~7°	Y	Brief event
3	28.01.2015	20-21 h; 22-24 h	PS	~150-270°	L	~30°	7-5°	N	
4	01.02.2015 - 02.02.2015	~22 h; ~1 h	PS +PM	150-180°	L	~27-32°	~7°	N	
5	04.02.2015	23-24 h	PS	~200°	L	~27°	~12°	N	
6	07.02.2015	~3 h	PM	~180°	L	~27°	~10°	N	
7	09.02.2015	~23 h	PS	~200°	L	~27°	~12°	N	Weak

N	Date	Time interval	Classification	Azimuth range	Elevation range	IPP		GM storm (Y/N)	Comments
						Latitudinal range, N	Longitudinal range, W		
8	11.02.2015	~23 h	PS	~200-210°	L	~27°	~12°	N	
9	14.02.2015	~21 h	PS	~160-170°	L	25-27°	~7°	N	
10	16.02.2015	~21 h	PS	150-180°	L	27-32°	~7°	N	
11	19.02.2015	~21 h	PS	~160°	L	27-32°	~7°	N	
12	28.02.2015	~20 h	PS	~160°	L	27-30°	~7°	N	
13	05.03.2015	~21 h	PS	~210°	L	27-30°	~12°	N	
14	06.03.2015	20 h; 21 h; 23-24 h	PS	~130°; ~150°; ~200°	L	27-30°; ~30°; ~32°	~12°; ~5°; ~0°	N	Long
15	09.03.2015	~1 h	PM	~180°	L	~30°	~10°	N	
16	14.03.2015	~1 h	PM	~180°	L	~30°	~10°	N	
17	21.03.2015	~23 h	PS	~180°	L	~27°	~10°	N	
18	26.03.2015	20-21 h	PS	~150°; ~180°	L	27-30°; ~30°	~10°; ~5°	N	Long
19	28.03.2015 - 29.03.2015	21 h; 22 h; 0 h; 1 h; 3 h	PS +PM	~140°; ~150°; 170-190	L	27-30°	~10°; ~7-9°; ~5°	N	Long
20	02.04.2015	~22 h	PS	~180°	L	27-30°	~10°	N	
21	04.04.2015	21-22 h	PS	~150°; ~180°	L	27-30°; ~30°	~10°; ~5°	N	
22	16.04.2015 - 17.04.2015	21 h; 23 h; 2 h	PS +PM	~170-190	L	27-30°; ~27°	~10°; ~8°	Y	Long
23	18.04.2015 - 19.04.2015	22-23 h; 0 h;	PS +PM	~150°; ~170°	L	27-30°; 30°	~10°; ~7°	N	2 days

N	Date	Time interval	Classification	Azimuth range	Elevation range	IPP		GM storm (Y/N)	Comments
						Latitudinal range, N	Longitudinal range, W		
24	19.04.2015	20-21 h	PS	~180°	L	~30°	~5°	N	2 days
25	23.04.2015 - 24.04.2015	23 h; 0 h	PS +PM	~150°	L	~30°	~7°	N	2 days
26	24.04.2015 - 25.04.2015	23 h; 1 h	PS +PM	~180°; ~150°	L	~30°; ~27°	~5°; ~9°	N	2 days
27	30.04.2015	~22 h	PS	~160°	L	~30°	~5°	N	
28	04.05.2015	23 h	PS	~170°	L	~27°	~5°	N	
29	22.06.2015 - 23.06.2015	20-21 h; 23-24 h; ~2 h	PS +PM	120- 200°; ~240°	A	~35°; 35-37°; 35-37°	~20°; 10-7°; 5°	Y	Long and strong
30	07.09.2015	20 h; 23 h	PS	~170°; ~180°; ~200°	L	~27°; 27-30°	~10°; ~7°	Y	Long
31	25.09.2015	22 h	PS	~180°	L	27-30°	~10°	N	
32	24.10.2015	21 h; 22-24 h	PS	~170°; ~180°; ~200°	L	27-30°; ~27°; ~27°	~12°; ~10°; ~5°	N	2 days
33	25.10.2015	20-21 h	PS	~180°; ~200°	L	~27°; ~27°	~12°; ~10°	N	2 days
34	29.10.2015	19 h; 21-22 h	PS	~180°; ~200°	L	~30°; 27-30°	~12°; ~10°	N	Long
35	25.11.2015	0 h	PM	~160°	L	~27°	~5°	N	
36	27.11.2015	21 h	PS	~175°	L	~27°	~7°	N	
37	18.12.2015	20 h; 22 h	PS	~180°	L	~27°	~10°	N	Long
38	06.03.2016 - 07.03.2016	22-24 h	PS +PM?	~180°	L	27-30°	~10°	Y	Long
39	07.04.2016	22 h	PS	~190°	L	~30°; ~32°	~12°; ~10°	Y	

6.3. The event of June 22-23, 2015

The SE on June 22-23, 2015, is a well-known event (see, e.g., Cherniak & Zakharenkova, 2016) when an equatorial plasma bubbles spilled-over from their usual low latitudes (25° S – 25° N) and caused scintillation events observed by instruments in the South-European region. To our knowledge, this event was previously analysed using only ROTI and TEC data (GIM and satellite data). Here, for the first time, we present an analysis using S4 data and obtained from a local ground receiver.

[Figure 15](#) shows time variations of the S4 index for two days, June 22 and 23 of 2015; [Fig. 16](#) shows azimuth-elevation distribution of S4 during this time interval, while [Fig. 17](#) shows IPP positions for satellites experiencing scintillations. The studied Se took place during the night. It started around 20 h LT on June 22 and ended before 3 h LT in June 23. There were four sub-events:

1. 20:00-21:00 LT on June 22 seen in the signal of southward located satellites at all elevations – marked as A in [Figs. 15, 16](#) and [17](#);
2. 21:30-22:30 LT on June 22 seen in the signal of southward located satellites at all elevations – marked as B in [Figs. 15, 16](#) and [17](#);
3. 22:45-23:45 LT on June 22 seen in the signal of southward located satellites at all elevations – marked as C in [Figs. 15, 16](#) and [17](#);
4. 02:00-02:30 on June 23 seen in the signal of southward located satellites at $\sim 30^{\circ}$ elevation – marked as D in [Figs. 15, 16](#) and [17](#).

Figure 15. Time variations of S4 during June 22-23, 2015. Letters A-D mark several scintillation sub-events that took place during the night June 22-23.

Figure 16. Azimuth-elevation distribution of S4 during June 22-23, 2015. For A-D see Figure 15.

Figure 17. IPP of satellites with $S4 > 0.6$ during June 22-23, 2015: top panel – low elevation satellites, bottom panel – high elevation satellites. For A-D see Figure 15.

Figure 18 shows changes of IPP and corresponding $S4$ from June 22 19:30 to June 23 02:30 as animated maps. As one can see, there was a hint to a westward drift of scintillation sources (A – C in Figs. 15, 16 and 17), mostly in the signal of the low elevation satellites (compare Fig. 17 and 18).

Further studies using both SI and TEC data for the South European -East Midlatitudinal Atlantic Ocean are needed to fully understand the dynamics of the June 2015 SE event.

Figure 18. Animated S4 IPP maps (satellites at all elevations).

5. References

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6. Data availability

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8. Supplementary material

Figure S1. S4 variations as function of an hour for individual months: from December 2014 to November 2015. Black dots show S4 values obtained during geomagnetically quiet time intervals, and red dots show S4 obtained for geomagnetically disturbed periods.

Figure S2. Same as Fig. S1 but from December 2015 to November 2016.

Figure S3. Same as Fig. S1 but from December 2016 to August 2017 and from October 2017 to December 2017.